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VOCAL TO LOCAL AS EFFECTIVE RETAIL MARKETING STRATEGIES

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Abstract

The primary research objective is to determine the influence of Vocal to Local strategy on retail sector in India. The setting for this study was the retail industries of Maharashtra. Qualitative semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted with seven retailer industry of Maharashtra. The result of study shows retail industry had experienced the impact of Vocal to Local strategy on buying behavior of customers, customer satisfaction and customer retention. This study concludes that Vocal to Local strategy has a positive impact on retail industry.

Keywords: Vocal to local, Retail industry, Local strategy, Buying behavior, Customer

Introduction

Vocal for Local' is a concept which dates back to the era of the Swadeshi movement which started in 1905 as part of the Indian independence movement. As an economic strategy, it helped develop Indian nationalism at the time. After 1947, in the 1950s and 60s we followed a

conscious, socialist pattern of development to create and grow a base of domestic big industry. However, this minimized competition and also encouraged protectionism. The era of the 1990s saw a liberalization of the economies across the world, including in India. This led to an infusion of FDI and big investments from MNCs and corporate houses and several joint ventures which made India very competitive.

So 'Vocal for Local' would have been a brilliant strategy for some sectors in India but definitely not in most of the sectors. While 'Vocal for Local' is a great idea, we have to recognise that the realities of the global environment have changed significantly. It is no longer possible to create globally competitive products without access to globally competitive resources, and without creating globally competitive synergies

Indians must use domestically made products to replace foreign ones as their resolution for the New Year said Prime Minister Narendra Modi on his Maan Ki Baat program on 27th Dec.2020 Sunday, reiterating his government's plan to become "self reliant" in manufacturing." he appeal to the citizen to make a list of goods of daily-use imported articles that have unconsciously become part of their lives and made them their captive. He urge the citizen let us find out their Indian alternatives and resolve to use products produced by the hard work of Indians,".

The people of India have taken many steps forward and are getting vocal for local. Due to that the manufacturers are also thinking about making top quality products. This will boost the efforts towards Aatmanirbhar Bharat. The focus on Made-in-India products the manufacturers should not compromise with the quality of materials produced by them with zero effect, zero defect' policy. In this connection different retail industries are taking various steps to promote local product in their marketing strategy.

The Covid-19 has negatively impacted the retail sector. With all the retail shops and sectors being closed to ward off the crisis, sales and manufacturing have plummeted to the ground.

Retail industries hope to see a positive change now as restrictions have been eased and shops being reopened. Although not at full swing but customer footfall has started. Similarly, online business is resuming at a good pace.

Further to support local for vocal – retail industries are also engaged with local supplier and manufacturers. They had partnered with them to fulfill their business requirements along with educating and developing them to achieve fast, cost effective and best quality output.

The COVID 19 pandemic is forcing changes in the world. People are living differently, thinking differently and in many ways buying differently. Consumers are looking at products and brands through a new lens. The factors that influence brand decisions are also changing as “Buy Local trend accelerates”.

Literature Review

Srivastava, D. (2020) emphasized the Indian heritage and marketing goods with the clear 'Made in India' slogan. In terms of customer preference following the failure during the shutdown, Swadeshi goods are also demanded to support the economy.

Chakraborty (2020) investigated global trends from an Indian viewpoint it attempts to discover emerging issues in local governance. A decade of indecisiveness and the corruption along with the role of social media exposures to perceived threats from cross-border terror have given birth to central political forces and the current era has seen an increase in the Capacity of state the Indian administration is not permitted to judge on local issues from a grassroots level.

Behrman, A. (2021) stated after getting the slogan of becoming ‘Atma-Nirbhar’ to mitigate the impact of COVID-19, it seems that in future ‘Made in India’ will be a significant factor to influence the consumer buying behaviour. They tried to explore the changes in advertising campaigns adopted by selected FMCG companies to boost the Indian economy and common themes to support the ‘Vocal for Local’ movement.

Chatterjee, A. (2020) stated maintaining the public health infrastructure requires easy availability of medicines at affordable cost, especially in times of epidemics. This makes the pharmaceutical industry an important strategic asset to support the ‘Vocal for Local’ movement.

Objectives of study

- I. To study impact of local product on customer satisfaction in retail store
- II. To analyze the influence of local product on customer retention in retail store.

Hypotheses

H1 - There is a significant positive relation between the presence and absence of a local product in a retail store and customer satisfaction

H2- The constant offering of local products helps increase customer retention.

Scope and Need of the study

This research aim to explore the impact of Vocal to Local strategy on buying behavior of customers, customer satisfaction and customer retention in small retail industries of Maharashtra, it also provide a path to implement Vocal to Local strategy and managing retail industries smoothly. This paper also explained and provides different insight to small retail industries of Maharashtra.

Research Methods

This explorative, comparative qualitative paper explores business practices and marketing strategies by small retail business owners in India and the role of localization, using three key themes – place, people and promotion.

Analysis Method

To achieve the objectives described above, and to analyze their importance among consumers in retail sectors, 5 point Likert-scale used to allow the author of this study to gather the necessary data to calculate the mean and correlations among the questions described previously, as well as other statistical information that was needed to interpret respondents' perceptions such as standard deviation for the overall results on each topic.

Results

Participant Profile Demographic results of a total of 114 valid surveys were as follows: -

Gender: Male 48.00%, Female 52.00% -

Marital Status: Married 58.02%, Single 41.98% -

Age: Under 20 0.88%, 21-30 35.96%, 31-40 33.33%, 41-50 26.32%, Above 50 3.51% -

Educational Level: Secondary Education 21.93%, Bachelor Degree 64.04%, Master Degree 14.04% - **Occupation:** Professional 8.77%, Retired 0.88%, House Wife 1.75%, Student 5.26%,

Worker 16.67%, Self-Employed 22.81%, Unemployed 5.26%, Private Sector Employee 35.96%, Other 2.63%

Income Level: Less Than Rs 10000per Month 33.33%, Rs 10000-Rs-15000 per month 30.70%, Rs-15000-20000 per month 25.44%, Rs-20000-Rs-25000 per month 6.14%, Rs-25000-Rs30000 per month 2.63%, above 30000 1.75%

For **H1**, "There is a significant positive relation between the presence or absence of a local product in a retail store and customer satisfaction ", correlation between local product and customer satisfaction was analyzed and a result of +8.002% was obtained. Therefore, it can be inferred that by having a positive correlation between local product and customer satisfaction, which means that when there is a greater impact of vocal to local strategy on retail industry. For **H2**, "The constant offering of local products helps increase customer retention ", correlation between local products and customer retention analyzed and a result of 15.176% was obtained. Therefore, it can be inferred that when local products and customer retention are highly correlated with each other. Therefore, the hypothesis may also be considered as valid.

Conclusions and Discussion

As a result of all what has been described within this document, it can be concluded that when local product has a greater impact on customer satisfaction's perception tends to grow on the positive side, confirming that a localized marketing strategy taking into consideration local customs and values, helps increase up to certain point the attractiveness towards a new product within a new market, and makes valid the fact than in India, Another aspect to consider is the fact that induction of local product also influence customer's retention. Therefore, it is clear that vocal to local as effective retail marketing strategies for small retailing business in India. As a result of this, innovation cannot be ignored since it comes to stimulate the necessary brand differentiation and demand in any marketing strategy that may involves local products, especially within a business environment. Consequently, this innovation process should be dynamic and constant, when necessary, to remain competitive and retain actual customers especially on those areas where the business has developed a competitive advantage (Bowonder, Dambal, Kumar &Shirodkar, 2010; Francesca, Ciommi, Donatella & Enrico, 2010). Last but not

least, through this research has also been validated the fact that vocal to local as effective retail marketing strategies for small retailing business in India and may have a competitive advantage, benefit of being associated with a better service or quality, thus increasing customer's perception and satisfaction. Nevertheless, it becomes fundamental to understand that local brands are developed with time, and that depending on the culture and customs of the market being penetrated, if such cultural aspects are not handled correctly they become a advantage compared to other options (Akaka & Alden, 2010; Jun, Lee & Gentry, 2005; Harish, 2008). Finally, a good product brings with it more customer loyalty, and such customer loyalty means more sales, growth, and even survival within difficult times.

References

1. Akaka, M. A., & Alden, D. L. (2010). Global brand positioning and perceptions: International advertising and global consumer culture. *International journal of Advertising*, 29(1), 37-56.
2. Atul Kumar (2011), "Demographic & Geographic Inclination towards Store Design: A Study of Shopping Mall Customers in Maharashtra-State, India", *Asian Journal of Management*, Vol. 2, Issue 3: July-Sept, pp. 87-93
3. Atul Kumar (2012), "Store Image - A Critical Success Factor in Dynamic Retailing Environment: An Investigation", *Asian Journal of Management*, Vol. 3, Issue 1: January-March, pp. 01-05
4. Atul Kumar (2012), "The Changing Buying Behaviour of Customers in Organized Retail Sector of Pune City", *International Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, Vol. 2, Issue 1: February, pp. 242-263
5. Atul Kumar, Jena Joshi and VinaydeepBrar (2019), "Impact of Sales Promotion on Customer Purchase Intention with respect to Organized Retail Industry", *International Journal for Research in Engineering Application & Management*, Vol. 05, Issue 02, May, pp. 905-913
6. Behrman, A. (2021). Global and local dimensions of vocal dynamics. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 105(1), 432-443.

7. Bowonder, B., Dambal, A., Kumar, S., &Shirodkar, A. (2010). Innovation strategies for creating competitiveadvantage. *Research-technology management*, 53(3), 19-32.
8. Chakraborty (2020), U. Vocal for Local: Reviewing Global Experience with an Indian Insight.
9. Chatterjee, A. (2020). Vocal for Local: Incentive Schemes for Pharmaceutical API Industry. *The Management Accountant Journal*, 55(10), 25-27.
10. Francesca, A., Ciommi, M., Donatella, F., & Enrico, V. (2010). International Specialization and Vertical Differentiation. *Annals of the University of Oradea*, 19(1), 153-158.
11. Harish, R. (2008). Building a Global Brand Through the Local Route. *ICFAI Journal of International Business*, 3(3).
12. Jun, S., Lee, H., & Gentry, J. W. (2005). Effects of Global Cultural Positioning Advertisements. *ACR Asia-Pacific Advances*.
13. Kumar, A., Brar, V., &Wadajkar, V. (2019). Significance of effective HRM practices in organized retail sector - A literature review. *International Journal of Enhanced Research in Educational Development*, 7(1), 22-26.
14. Kumar, A.,&Brar, V. (2018). Digital marketing and role of blockchain in digital marketing industry. *International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Methods*,6(12), 23-26.
15. Srivastava, D. (2020, June). Being Vocal for Local Brands: A New Mantra of Success for Indian FMCG Companies. In *National Multidisciplinary E-Conference on Opportunities and Challenges for Indian Business: Self Reliance and Development through Vocal for Local to Global approach–2020*.

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